

Antibiotic resistance of *Aeromonas hydrophila* isolated from frog *Hoplobatrachus occipitalis* consumed in Côte d'Ivoire

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Abstract

Aeromonas hydrophila is an opportunistic microorganism. It is widely involved in frog infections. *Hoplobatrachus occipitalis* is the species of frog most consumed in the different localities of Côte d'Ivoire. This research aimed to study the extracellular virulence factors and antibiotic resistance profiles of *A. hydrophila* strains isolated from *H. occipitalis*. The determination of extracellular virulence factors were performed onto 113 strains of *A. hydrophila* isolated from frogs *H. occipitalis* using conventional methods. The antimicrobial susceptibility tests were performed by the disk diffusion method using 20 isolates of *A. hydrophila*. All strains isolated produce nuclease (100%) but the ability to produce haemolysins, lipases, amylases and proteases varied from one isolate to another These microorganisms were the most resistant to Amoxicillin (95%), Ampicillin (90%), Tetracyclin (85%), Ceftriaxone (80%) Chloramphenicol (75%). All strains of *A. hydrophila* have developed multi-resistance to different antibiotics used. The multiple antibiotic resistance indices ranged from 0.41 to 0.83. These data show the degree of pathogenicity of the strains isolated from frogs. The consumption of this species could constitute a threat to consume them if hygiene measures are not taken into account.

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Introduction

Frogs today constitute a very popular food source on the African continent. They are appreciated because of their nutritional characteristics and their taste which is compared to that of chickens (Mohneke *et al.*, 2010). Thus in Burkina Faso, Nigeria and Ivory Coast the consumption rates were respectively 67%, 43% and 55.2% (Mohneke *et al.*, 2010 ; Onadeke *et al.*, 2011; Ble *et al.*, 2016). These frogs are now disappearing due to several diseases, the most important of which is that caused by *Aeromonas hydrophila*. These frogs are disappearing today for causes linked to several diseases.

Aeromonas sp. is part of the microbial flora of the skin and intestines of healthy frogs but can cause disease in these animals. It is responsible for “red leg diseases” and is involved in cases of mass mortality of frogs in captivity and in the natural environment (Forbes *et al.*, 2004). This presence in frogs may also constitute a public health risk for consumers because *A. hydrophila* is an emerging pathogen involved in gastroenteritis, septicemia and endocarditis (Stratev *et al.*, 2012). The areas where frogs are caught are generally shallows, abandoned fish ponds of questionable microbiological quality.

It should be noted that in aquaculture areas, antibiotics are used to prevent and treat bacterial diseases. Furthermore, their use leads to an increase in the prevalence of multi-resistant bacteria which represent health risks (Koudou *et al.*, 2020).

In Côte d'Ivoire, studies have reported the existence of *A. hydrophila* in fish and resistance to antibiotics has also been reported (Kouassi *et al.*, 2018; Kone *et al.*, 2022). Concerning strains of *A. hydrophila* isolated from frogs, there is no data on antibiotic resistance.

Monitoring the resistance of zoonotic bacteria is particularly important to better assess the risks to human health linked to contact with animals or the consumption of food of animal origin. The objective of this study was to investigate the antibiotic

resistance profiles of *A. hydrophila* strains isolated from frogs.

Material and methods

Origin of Aeromonas hydrophila isolates

The *A. hydrophila* strains used in this study come from wild frog *H. occipitalis* which were purchased in three local markets in western Côte d'Ivoire: these are ISSIA, DALOA and SINFRA. These strains had been isolated in a previous study using the method of Sarka *et al.* (2012) then stored in the Laboratory at -20°C. Note that the frogs sold on the markets are captured in ponds and shallows. These environments are characterized by a high level of anthropogenic impact, resulting from agricultural and livestock activities in certain cases.

In vitro virulence test of Aeromonas

The search for virulence factors was carried out on 113 strains of *A. hydrophila* distributed as follows: Issia (38 strains), Daloa (38 strains) and Sinfra (37 strains). Five tests were performed in this study.

Hemolytic activity

The hemolytic activity was determined by streak of the strains of *A. hydrophila* onto agar base (Bio-Rad, France) supplemented with 5% sheep blood (Hadeel and Majeed, 2011).

Nuclease activity

Extracellular nucleases (DNases) were determined on DNase agar plates (Difco) from 24-h colonies isolated on alkaline nutrient agar (Castro-Escarpulli *et al.*, 2003).

Proteolytic activity

Casein hydrolysis of *A. hydrophila* were tested on nutritive agar containing 1.5% skimmed (Olaniran *et al.*, 2015).

Lipolytic activity

Lipase activity was carried out by culturing the strains on 0.5% tributyrin agar (Panreac, Barcelona, Spain) emulsified with 0.2% Triton X100 (Castro-Escarpulli *et al.*, 2003).

Amylase activity

Was performed by streak of the isolates onto nutrient agar (Bio-Rad, France) supplemented with 0.4% (W/V) starch in PBS.

Determination of the phenotypic level of antibiotic resistance

A total of 20 isolates of *A. hydrophila* were examined for their resistance to 12 different antibiotics using the disk diffusion method recommended by Bauer *et al.* 1966. The antibiotics and concentration ranges tested were as follows: Amoxicillin (AX, 25 µg), Ampicillin (AMP, 10 µg), Cefatoxime (CTX, 30 µg), Ceftazidime (CAZ, 30 µg), Ceftriaxone (CRO, 30 µg), Chloramphenicol (C, 30 µg), Gentamicin (CN, 10 µg), Imipenem (IPM, 10 µg), Kanamycin (K, 30 µg), Oxytetracycline (OT, 30 µg), Streptomycin (S, 10 µg), Tetracycline (TE, 30 µg). The diameter of the inhibition zone was measured and interpreted in

accordance with guidelines of the Antibiogram Committee of the French Society of Microbiology. The multiple antibiotic resistances (MAR) index was calculated by dividing the number of antibiotics to which the bacteria were resistant by the total number of antibiotics studied (Sarter *et al.*, 2007).

Data analysis

SPSS 20.0 (IBM Corporation) was used to analyze the data. The MAR index, prevalence and antibiotic resistance of *Aeromonas* isolates were all presented as percentages. The data were analyzed using simple descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution and percentages.

Results

Virulence factor of *A. hydrophila* isolated from frog

The results presented in Fig. 1 show the pathogenicity of *A. hydrophila* isolated from frogs.

Table 1. Phenotype and MAR index of *A. hydrophila* isolated from frog.

MAR Phenotype	No. of antibiotic showing resistance	Strains code	% strains	MAR Index
AX-AMP-CTX-K-TE-CN-IPM	7	Aeh1	5	0.58 (7/12)
AX-AMP-CAZ-GN-IPM	5	Aeh3	5	0.41 (5/12)
AX-AMP-CRO-C-TE-GN-IPM	7	Aeh2, Aeh10, Aeh12, Aeh17	20	0.58 (7/12)
AX-AMP-CRO-K-TE	5	Aeh5	5	0.41 (5/12)
AX-AMP-CTX-CRO-C-TE-GN	7	Aeh4	5	0.58 (7/12)
AX-AMP-CTX-CRO-K-C-OT-S-TE-GN	10	Aeh14, Aeh18, Aeh20	15	0.83 (10/12)
AX-AMP-K-C-TE-GN-IPM	7	Aeh19	5	0.58 (7/12)
AX-CRO-S-TE-GN-IPM	6	Aeh15	5	0.50 (6/12)
AX-CRO-C-TE-IPM	5	Aeh11	5	0.41 (5/12)
AX-AMP-CTX-C-GN	5	Aeh8	5	0.41 (5/12)
AMP-CRO-C-OT-GN	5	Aeh9	5	0.41 (5/12)
AX-AMP-CRO-C-OT-TE-GN-IPM	8	Aeh16	5	0.66 (8/12)
AX-AMP-CRO-K-C-OT-S-TE-IPM	9	Aeh7, Aeh6	10	0.75 (9/12)
AX-AMP-CRO-S-TE-GN-IPM	7	Aeh13	5	0.58 (7/12)

DNase production materialized by the presence of a clear halo around the colonies (Fig. 2a) was observed in all bacteria (100%). While the proportions of hemolysin (68.42- 91.8%), protease (54.04-68.45%), amylase (47.36-65.78%) and lipase (23.08-47.36%) varied according to the sampling site. The appearance of a clear halo observed in Fig. 2b shows that the strain produces β -hemolysin. Amylase activity is also indicated in Fig. 2c by the presence of a clear zone around the colonies.

Antibiotic resistance of *Aeromonas hydrophila* isolated

The antibiotic resistance study was carried out on 20 strains of *Aeromonas hydrophila* and is shown in Fig. 3. High resistance has been observed for most β -lactamase class antibiotics such as Amoxicillin (95%), Ampicillin (90%). High resistance was also observed with Tetracycline (85%), Ceftriaxone (80%) and Chloramphenicol (75%). However, low resistance was observed for cephalosporins such as Ceftazidime (5%)

and Cefatoxime (25%). All strains were resistant to Amoxillin except the Aeh9 strain which was susceptible. In addition, the strains showed resistance to at least five antibiotics.

The highest resistance profile was obtained with the Aeh14, Aeh18 and Aeh20 strains which showed resistance to 10 antibiotics out of the 12 tested. A total

four *A. hydrophila* isolates (20%) displayed presented the multi-resistance patterns of AX-AMP-CRO-C-TE-CN-IPM and three strains (15%) expressed the patterns of AX-AMP-CTX-CRO-K-C-OT-S-TE-CN. The MAR which was resistance to more than two classes of antibiotics was recorded in all strains of *A. hydrophila*. The multi-resistance index of all isolates was ranged from 0.41 to 0.83 (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Virulence level of *A. hydrophila* isolated from *H. occipitalis*.

Discussion

Extracellular virulence factors

In this study, five virulence factors associated with the pathogenicity of *Aeromonas hydrophila* were highlighted. It appears that all strains were positive in the DNase test (100%) characterized by the formation of the clear zone around the colonies. These results are similar to those of Kone *et al.* (2022) who worked on strains of *A. hydrophila* isolated from fish in Côte d'Ivoire. In addition, a study by Yadav *et al.* (2014) carried out on *A. hydrophila* showed 100% production of the DNase enzyme. These enzymes can be involved in bacterial nutrition but can also cause diseases in animals and humans (Pemberton *et al.*, 1997). The production of hemolysin by the strains was between 68.42-91.8% depending on the collection sites. This capacity for hemolysin production has already been revealed in several studies, particularly on fish. In fact, the hemolysin production rates were respectively 89.5% and 78.95% in the study of Kone *et al.* (2022) and John *et al.* (2013). This presence of hemolysin in our study shows that these strains are

pathogenic. Indeed according to Takahashi *et al.* (2014) hemolysin produced by *A. hydrophila* would be a very important virulence factor. It is considered the main virulence factor of *A. hydrophila*, which exhibits hemolytic and enteric toxicity and is encoded by the *ahh1* gene.

The mature, biologically active hemolysin secreted by *A. hydrophila* can bind to and damage the host target cell. This study showed that the isolated strains also produced protease (54.04-68.45%), amylase (47.36-65.78%) and lipase (23.08 - 47.36%). The protease production rate was 72.4% in *A. hydrophila* fish (Kone *et al.*, 2022). Their detection in our strains is an indicator of the pathogenicity of *A. hydrophila* because the protease damages tissues and is involved in the etiology of infections (McMahon, 2000). As for lipases, although they are involved in the nutrition of the bacteria, they alter the structure of the cytoplasmic membrane of the host and intensify its pathogenicity with the presence of the aerolysin gene (Nawaz *et al.*, 2010).

Fig. 2. Some virulence tests of *A. hydrophila* isolated from *H. occipitalis* a: Detection of DNase production on DNase agar, b: detection of hemolysin production of blood agar, c: detection of amylase production on nutrient agar supplemented of 4% starch.

Multi-resistance to antibiotic of Aeromonas hydrophila

Antibiotic resistance tests carried out on 20 strains of *A. hydrophila* isolated from frogs in this study show that these strains are more resistant to β -lactamases such as Amoxicillin (95%) and Ampicillin (90%). These results confirm the previously reported high resistance of *A. hydrophila* to a wide range of the β -lactam antibiotics family. According to Saavedra *et al.*

(2004), strains of *A. hydrophila* develop natural resistance to antibiotics from the β -lactamase family. Contradictory to our finding, high resistance to amoxicillin (98%) and ampicillin (93%) were observed in the work of Koné *et al.* (2022).

The present study showed that *Aeromonas* strains isolated from frog were characterised by their resistance to TE (85%), CRO (80%), C (75%).

Fig. 3. Frequency of antibiotic resistance of 20 isolates of *A. hydrophila*.

AX: Amoxicillin, AMP: Ampicillin, CTX: Cefatoxime, CAZ: Ceftazidime, CRO: Ceftriaxone, C: Chloramphenicol, GN: Gentamicin, IPM: Imipenem, K: Kanamycine, OT: Oxytetracycline, S: Streptomycin, TE: Tetracycline.

These results confirm previous research that reported high resistance to the antibiotics cited (Elkamouny *et al.*, 2020). The resistance to antibiotics such as GN (55%) and C (75%) obtained in our work are contrary

to the results of Rakici *et al.* (2021) who recorded 0% resistance of strains isolated from *Pelophylax* sp frogs. This variation in antibiotic resistance could be linked to the sources of *A. hydrophila*, the frequency

and types of antimicrobials previously used in areas where these animals are captured (Son *et al.*, 1997). Gentamycin resistance (55%) and susceptibility (35%) in this work therefore calls for concern because aeromonads has been largely reported to be sensitive to Gentamycin although there are reports of resistance as well (Jalal *et al.*, 2010). All strains of *A. hydrophila* tested (100%) presented multi-resistance to antibiotics because the MAR index is greater than 0.2 (MAR index > 0.2). These results reveal that the frog represents a source of risky consumption. Highest MAR index (0.83) was observed in three isolates (15%) coded Aeh14, Aeh18 and Aeh20 while low MAR index (0.41) was reported in 25% of strains. Our result is in line with some studies where the capabilities of these bacteria to develop resistance and transmit such effectively have been established. MAR index was between 0.67 and 0.89 in strains of *A. hydrophila* isolated from the fish *Clarias gariepinus* in Nigeria (Sarka *et al.*, 2017).

Thi *et al.* (2023) also recorded multi-resistance of their strains with a MAR index ranged from 0.33 to 0.92. One of the reasons which could explain this multi-resistance mentioned in our study would be the unsanitary state of the water in which the frogs are caught. In fact, the capture takes place in shallows, puddles, and abandoned fish ponds into which wastewater is continually discharged. Thi *et al.* (2023) established a link between MAR and wastewater discharged into rivers.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that DNase production is considered as a virulence factor most observed in isolated *Aeromonas* strains followed by hemolysin (68.42-91.8%). In addition, multi-resistance to antibiotics was recorded in all strains with a MAR index value greater than 0.2.

This indicates that the isolates come from high-risk sources such as ponds, ponds, shallows which are areas where frogs are caught. The issue of surveillance frog catching areas must be among our priorities to reduce human contamination.

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